

Reimagining EAP in the Age of GenAI: Innovation, Integrity, and the Future of Assessment

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ABSTRACT

English for Academic Purposes (EAP) programs play a critical role in preparing students with English as an additional language for academic success in Australian universities. The internationalisation of higher education in Australia, driven by increased global mobility and shifting student demographics, has transformed the landscape of teaching, learning, and assessment in higher education. As universities adapt to the demands of a diverse and digitally connected student body, they must respond not only to linguistic and cultural diversity but also to the pedagogical implications of multimodal learning, digital collaboration, and the rise of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI). This article presents a dual-track assessment regime at two Australian university English language centres, Macquarie University College and Monash University English Language Centre,

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which offer high-stakes EAP programs for direct entry to university. The centres combine secure, invigilated checkpoints for progression decisions with guided, AI-assisted assessment for learning, aligned with regulatory expectations for direct entry programs. Drawing on policy analysis from the centres, the article contributes a practice-informed illustration of how EAP programs can integrate AI literacy, feedback literacy, and genre pedagogy while preserving credible evidence of unassisted performance. Emerging assessment designs and the application of GenAI in assessment development and feedback are discussed, alongside key risks and mitigation strategies. The paper concludes with implications for EAP programs that aim to equip students to navigate the complexities of contemporary higher education and make meaningful contributions to global academic communities.

Keywords: academic integrity, assessment, English for Academic Purposes, English language assessment, generative AI, target language use domain, higher education

INTRODUCTION

The increased global mobility of recent decades has led to the internationalisation of higher education (HE) in Australia, with students from diverse cultural backgrounds now forming part of student communities nationwide. This shifting demographic, alongside developments in communication technologies, generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) and an increasingly competitive global marketplace, has played a pivotal role in reshaping learning and teaching practices. Even prior to COVID-19, universities were witnessing the expansion of multimodality, interactivity, and collaboration in pedagogical approaches, as educators sought ways to integrate, engage, and socialise diverse cohorts of domestic and international students (Arkoudis et al., 2013).

In preparation for tertiary studies in Australia, international students with English as an additional language (EAL) can demonstrate the required level of English language proficiency by successfully completing an English for academic purposes (EAP) program at a registered English Language Intensive Courses for Overseas Students (ELICOS) centre. EAP programs are designed to prepare students from diverse cultural and educational backgrounds for their studies while ensuring they develop the requisite level of English proficiency. Programs run between 5 and 25 weeks, and on successful completion, EAL students are deemed to have sufficient language skills to undertake further studies in higher education or vocational education and training.

To ensure relevance and authenticity in their program design, EAP program developers monitor learning and assessment trends in the target language use (TLU) domain, specifically in universities. As pedagogical practices continue to evolve in response to shifting student demographics, technological advancements, and global academic standards, developers seek to align EAP curricula with the expectations of HE institutions. The recent proliferation of GenAI tools has further complicated this landscape, raising new questions about academic integrity, authorship, and the role of AI-assisted writing in student work. In response, EAP programs are increasingly tasked with not only refining language instruction but also embedding academic literacies, digital and AI literacies, ethical considerations, and assessment methods that reflect current university practices. By doing so, they aim to better equip students with the skills and competencies required to successfully navigate their chosen fields of study in an AI-augmented academic environment.

In the context of contemporary education, the purpose of education has shifted from merely acquiring knowledge to developing skills that enable learners to navigate, evaluate, and apply information across diverse cultural and disciplinary landscapes (Bearman et al., 2024). Knowledge is now broadly distributed, and 21st-century learners are expected to engage critically with vast networks of information (Bearman et al., 2024). For EAL students, this means that developing language proficiency alone is insufficient; they must also cultivate academic literacies, intercultural competence, and digital fluency to thrive in contemporary HE.

An additional challenge is that ELICOS EAP programs with direct entry arrangements to universities must comply with the requirements of the Tertiary Education Quality Standards Agency (TEQSA), the education regulator responsible for upholding the quality and reputation of Australian higher education awards. TEQSA stipulates that assessment outcomes must be comparable to other admission criteria for the tertiary course of study. According to the *TEQSA Direct Entry Guide*, these criteria include recognised frameworks such as the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) or the Pearson Global Scale of English (GSE), as well as international proficiency tests such as the International English Language Testing System (IELTS) and the Pearson Test of English (PTE) Academic, among others (TEQSA, 2023).

This article explores how EAP programs are responding to these contemporary challenges in HE while retaining compliance with TEQSA requirements. It

examines how curriculum design, assessment practices, and pedagogical approaches within EAP programs are evolving to support the development of academic literacies, intercultural competence, and digital fluency – key capabilities for success in HE. In doing so, it considers the tension between innovation and regulatory accountability, and how programs navigate the dual imperative of preparing students for academic rigour while ensuring assessment comparability with university admission standards. The article begins by examining broader shifts in learning and assessment across the sector before turning to policy and practice at two university language centres - Macquarie University College and Monash College English Language Centre - to illustrate how Australian institutions are adapting to the opportunities and risks posed by global forces, emerging technologies, and GenAI.

THE CHANGING TARGET LANGUAGE USE (TLU) DOMAIN IN HE

Prior to the launch of ChatGPT in November 2022, learning and teaching practices in HE were incrementally adapting to the external forces of changing student demographics and technological advancements. In a study of HE teaching practices, Arkoudis et al. (2013) noted that cultural and linguistic diversity, brought about by internationalisation, is leveraged as a resource for learning and teaching by promoting cross-cultural syndicate groups of students to undertake problem-based, team-based, and project-based learning. Even the traditional teacher-centred lecture has morphed into multimodal events incorporating dialogic, active, and interactive teaching (French & Kennedy, 2016), while emerging pedagogies are focused on engaging students in real-world tasks that furnish them with graduate capabilities such as critical thinking, problem-solving, teamwork, sustainability, and ethical practice (Thomas et al., 2009). In turn, preparatory EAP programs have also been adapting to provide students with opportunities to develop the appropriate socio-cultural, interactional, and discourse competencies necessary for them to participate meaningfully in these educational activities.

A growing trend in HE is micro-modular course design, which breaks traditional curricula into smaller, targeted units. Although common in the USA, UK, and New Zealand, it is a relatively recent development in Australia (Ellis, 2018). This format allows students to tailor their studies to their personal interests, career goals, or skill gaps. For institutions, it streamlines curriculum development, as modules can serve multiple programs. However, the need to assess each module within a

semester raises concerns about fragmented learning and excessive assessment (Harland, 2020), which has been linked to workload and mental health issues among students and staff (Carter & Francis, 2022).

Another key trend in response to increasingly diverse student cohorts is the strategic use of assessment to guide student engagement. With students coming from varied educational and cultural backgrounds, managing cohorts has become challenging; consequently, it is not uncommon for lecturers to use frequent, low-weight summative assessments to encourage regular study habits and improve outcomes. However, this practice has raised concerns that this leads to compartmentalised learning (Harland & Wald, 2020). Additionally, the subsequent proliferation of poorly designed self-marking quizzes has contributed to the overassessment of low-level knowledge and the underassessment of higher-order skills, such as the application of knowledge (Boud, 2020).

The emergence of GenAI provides an opportunity to reset. Since the launch of ChatGPT in November 2022, thought leaders in HE (e.g., Liu & Bates, 2025) are calling for a rethink on the purpose and practice of higher education in the 21st century. They advocate for transformation over incremental change, while retaining the fundamental values of education, through cross-institutional collaboration to develop shared frameworks for governance, pedagogy, and assessment redesign (ibid). One of the most pressing issues is maintaining the integrity of university qualifications. Because GenAI can complete many take-home tasks, stand-alone unsupervised assignments are increasingly vulnerable as sole evidence of unassisted performance.

To support academic integrity efforts, TEQSA's emerging practice toolkit collates strategies and practices from HE institutions across Australia in their management of GenAI and academic integrity issues (TEQSA, 2024). Evidence of the toolkit's three key dimensions is apparent in the emerging trends of learning, teaching, and assessment. The self-assurance mechanisms embedded in the toolkit's dimension of *Process*, for example, can be seen in universities' adoption of strategies, risk management, governance, reporting, and monitoring protocols that support effective practice. The University of Sydney's two-lane approach to assessment, which has been largely influential in Australia, is a good example of this. Lane 1, *assured assessment of learning*, involves secured assessment, such as in-class contemporaneous assessment, viva voces or on-campus examinations, while Lane 2, *assessment as learning*, may incorporate human-AI collaboration (Liu & Bridgeman, 2023). Other universities have similarly leveraged the affordances of

Gen AI to design authentic assessments that target higher-order thinking skills through human-AI collaboration.

It is worth noting that other frameworks have classified assessment into finer levels. One is the AI Assessment Scale by Perkins et al. (2024), which includes five levels, ranging from no AI to AI-assisted idea generation and structuring, AI-assisted editing, AI task completion with human evaluation, and full AI. Another, even more nuanced framework is the six-lane version proposed by Steel (2024), which includes no assistance, simple editing assistance, planning/design assistance, assistance with attribution, GenAI software-based assessment, and 'not applicable,' where AI use is not helpful or relevant to completing an assessment.

The Toolkit's dimension of *People* refers to all levels of stakeholders within the HE ecosystem, such as academic, administrative, support personnel, students, and professional accreditation bodies. Professional development initiatives for staff and coaching initiatives for students in the use of GenAI are evidence of this dimension in action. An illustrative example is the emphasis on cultivating students' evaluative judgement regarding the outputs and processes of generative AI. Anticipating a future where the review of AI outputs is routine, Bearman et al. (2024) advocate emphasising critical thinking and evaluative judgement skills that will help students to evaluate and assess the reliability, relevance, and ethical implications of GenAI content. Cultivating students' capacity for responsible and informed engagement with emerging technologies is seen as key (Bearman et al., 2024; Liu & Bates, 2025).

An example of the toolkit's dimension of *Practice*, which operates at the level of teaching, learning, and assessment, can be found in the increasing use of viva voces and interactive oral assessment in HE. These methods allow instructors to directly engage with students' understanding, making it more challenging to rely on AI-generated responses (O'Riordan et al., 2025; Sotiriadou, 2020; Ward et al., 2023). Moreover, it is argued that oral assessments foster deeper learning by encouraging students to articulate their reasoning and reflect critically in real time (Shaeri et al., 2021; Ward et al., 2023).

CASE STUDIES

Policy and practices at Macquarie University and Monash University show alignment and divergence in their approaches to GenAI. Macquarie University's 2025 draft position statement to GenAI, for example, outlines four core principles:

(1) prioritising purpose over restriction by designing assessments that reflect AI's role in modern work; (2) promoting an emphasis on critical thinking, judgement, and appropriate tool usage over memory recall; (3) encouraging adaptability in using technology for problem solving; and (4) promoting ethical, values-based application of tools. All aspects of curriculum design, including assessment, are expected to adopt a programmatic approach, which entails shifting away from multiple micro-assessment tasks at the unit level to considering how assessment functions across the entire degree. Throughout the first part of 2025, in place of smaller, continuous assessment tasks, which were common in unit design, Macquarie has set a maximum of three assessment tasks for any unit. Plans are also underway to consolidate the number of assessment types to a more defined range within the university's curriculum management system. This work is a part of a well-being response to feedback about the impact of high assessment loads on students and staff.

By contrast, Monash University adopts programmatic assessment approaches, as recommended in TEQSA's guidance (Lodge et al., 2023), within a scaffolded suite that strategically integrates AI and utilises secure assessments where appropriate. In January 2025, it began a two-year Programmatic Assessment and Artificial Intelligence Review project to examine and recalibrate all coursework programs (Monash University, 2025b). This work sits within a broader effort to advance assessment by integrating AI strategically and using secure assessments where appropriate, within a coherent, scaffolded suite of activities that prepares students to operate effectively in the AI era. The principles of programmatic assessment rest on three pillars (Monash University, 2025a). First, feedback is continuous and meaningful, building learner agency and self-regulation. Second, a coherent mix of individual and collaborative assessment methods is selected with a clear educational rationale within the wider program and used holistically over time to provide multiple, scaffolded opportunities to demonstrate achievement across the program. Third, assessment decisions are equitable and credible, triangulating evidence across tasks and course learning outcomes within transparent policy frameworks. Collectively, these principles treat every assessment artefact as evidence, provide learners with multiple opportunities to review, reflect, and integrate feedback, and ensure defensible program-level judgments (Monash University, 2025a). The project is currently underway and is expected to lead to transformative assessment practices, regimes, and tasks across disciplines.

INNOVATIONS AND CHALLENGES IN EAP ASSESSMENT DESIGN

In response to the sweeping changes in the TLU domain, Australian EAP has evolved. EAP programs have traditionally focused on genre-based instruction with academic genres that have highly definable and teachable structures, such as research articles and academic presentations. Genre analysis, such as Swales' (1990) CARS model and Hyland's (2009) work on oral presentations, provides frameworks for understanding discourse structure, signposting, and sociocultural norms. These approaches expose students to target linguistic features and formulaic language, which they can apply in their own discourse. Other common academic genres include literature reviews, annotated bibliographies, case studies, and reports, which promote authentic assessment and transferable academic skills.

Even before the rise of GenAI in late 2022, tools like Grammarly had already raised concerns about academic integrity in EAP programs. With no policies in Australian universities or ELICOS centres addressing them, administrators faced uncertainty about how to classify their use and whether to ban such tools, adapt rubrics, or replace take-home assignments with invigilated assessments (Dinneen, 2021). With the recent and rapid advancement of GenAI, however, questions around how to assess students' language use with reliable and authentic assessment are even more pronounced.

The table below illustrates a range of GenAI tools that can be used to complete typical EAP assessment tasks, often requiring minimal language input from the student. While the GenAI output may include hallucinated sources and fabricated bibliographic citations (Walters & Wilder, 2023) or show weak domain-specific reasoning, they may well pass the assessment, as has been seen in law (Choi et al., 2022), medicine (Panthier & Gatinel, 2023), or humanities and social sciences (Farazouli et al., 2023).

Table 1. GenAI disruption of traditional EAP tasks

Assessment Task	Illustrative GenAI Tools
Literature reviews	Paperguide, Elicit, Semantic Scholar
Annotated bibliographies	Writefull, Zotero, ChatGPT
Presentations	CoPilot, Gamma.app, Canva
Writing reports and essays	ChatGPT, CoPilot, Perplexity, Claude, Gemini, Jasper
Videos	Synthesia, Animaker Deck, Galaxy AI, Veed.io, Akool

The realisation that these tasks, in their traditional forms, may have become obsolete as a means of assessing students' language skills is slowly spreading, although there are varying responses among ELICOS centres. At the 2025 University English Centres of Australia (UECA) Assessment Symposium, several centres reported using assignment instructions that explicitly permit or prohibit the use of GenAI, accompanied by rating rubrics that penalise language inconsistent with students' in-class performance. This approach, however, is difficult to police effectively, and it overlooks the fact that commonly used software, such as Microsoft Word, has built-in spelling and grammar checks that can legitimately enhance student output. Making decisions about which tools are allowed or disallowed and verifying compliance can lead to inconsistency among raters and ultimately undermine the reliability of assessment outcomes. It also raises the question of authenticity: if a student can legitimately use GenAI tools in practice in their university degrees, is it reasonable to deny them access or training for the use of these tools while they are in their preparatory program?

Macquarie University College (MQC) employs a sustainable assessment design (Boud & Soler, 2015), which meets the evaluative needs of the EAP program as well as the future needs of students at the university. Course design aims to strike a balance between advancing students' language proficiency while introducing AI literacy and fostering the development of appropriate sociocultural, interactional, and discourse competencies for university study. GenAI collaboration is integrated into learning and teaching activities for drafting, feedback, and comparative evaluation. It is also used in minor summative assessment tasks. Due to the high-stakes nature of the direct entry programs, MQC has allocated most of the assessment as *assured learning*, excluding the use of GenAI, so that students' real language use can be assessed. The table below shows the weighting of GenAI integrated assessments versus non-GenAI tasks, which are invigilated and handwritten.

Table 2. MQC Direct Entry 10 assessment weighting

MQC Direct Entry 10	Weighting	Assessment Task & Weighting
Assessment that incorporates GenAI	30%	Multimodal reflective journal Researched Oral Presentation
Assessment that excludes GenAI	70%	Integrated reading to write task Integrated listening to speak task Integrated reading, listening to write task

As an interim measure when GenAI first emerged, MQC replaced the traditional research essay with a process-based task focused on drafting, deadlines, and feedback. Submissions were supported by a resource folder containing original materials cited in student essays, along with follow-up interviews to ensure academic integrity. Although beneficial for developing academic skills, this approach was highly time-consuming and offered limited assessment of students' independent language use.

Concurrently, MQC was transitioning from separate skills tests to integrated skills assessments, which are better aligned with the TLU domain, where students draw on source texts to produce written or spoken output, such as essays and verbal reports. The use of these tasks revealed students' need for stronger summary and paraphrasing skills. Consequently, the research essay was removed to make space for coursework that prioritises targeted language development, feedback literacy, and multiple feedback points through self, peer, AI, and teacher review.

Monash University English Language Centre (MUELC), on the other hand, has adopted a dual strategy that combines assured assessment with guided, AI-assisted assessment. For assured assessments across all modules, the large, end-of-course online examinations introduced during the COVID-19 period (and proctored over Zoom) have been replaced by regular, lower-stakes online reading, listening, and writing tests delivered in Moodle using a secure browser called Safe Exam Browser and invigilated in class by teachers. Speaking is assessed directly through a range of tasks, including digital storytelling, video submissions, spoken reflections, group speaking tasks, tutorial discussions, and oral presentations, which provide multiple samples of students' performance.

For extended writing tasks, such as the Research Task in Module 4 (formerly the Monash English Bridging to university course), MUELC embeds GenAI authentically as part of the research process, while preserving the requirement

that students produce the final paper independently. Across the teaching weeks, students receive explicit instruction on using GenAI to brainstorm, develop structure and organisation, locate sources, and generate provisional reference lists. They are also taught to critically evaluate GenAI outputs, from checking for factual errors to assessing superficiality, cultural stereotyping, and fabricated sources. Students then learn how to substantiate their claims with appropriate academic literature rather than relying on AI-generated sources. Final papers are written without assistance and are assessed by the teacher, supported by a one-to-one interview in which students explain their ideas, demonstrate conceptual and process understanding, and discuss their use of GenAI.

Following a small-scale pilot involving 180 students and eight teachers (Hellema et al., 2024), MUELC introduced the AI-incorporated Research Task in the Module 4 program. In 2025, the task was refined to require each student to draft in a version-tracked online document (with edit history) and to maintain a research folder containing all source texts; both artefacts are accessible to teachers. While no mechanism can guarantee wholly unassisted writing, combining process history with a 10-minute viva voce provides teachers with deep insight into students' writing process, research practices, conceptual understanding, and transparency around GenAI use. Students reported feeling better equipped to collaborate with GenAI in a productive and ethical manner. MUELC reported a reduction of over 80% in suspected academic integrity breaches in 2025 (Sadeghpour, Module 4 Program Leader, 2025, personal communication), freeing staff time for targeted teaching and student support. In Module 4, the Research Task is paired with an invigilated Reflective Writing test. Together, the two tasks provide triangulated evidence of students' writing ability. The model is currently under consideration for adoption in lower-level modules (Modules 2 and 3), where GenAI is already used to support the creation of multimodal learning artefacts.

GENAI PRODUCTIVITY GAINS IN EAP CONTEXTS

The literature highlights growing productivity gains from GenAI in language teaching and learning (Chapelle, 2025; Koraiishi, 2023; Law, 2024). In Australian EAP programs, practitioners report that GenAI especially boosts efficiency in routine tasks, ideation, and content generation. Importantly, they stress the need for human-led critical evaluation, editing, and review of language assessment where construct-relevant decisions remain essential (e.g., Starford, 2024; Tran et al., 2024). In practice, this means EAP practitioners use GenAI to expand and

update assessment materials and to draft feedback, but do so within precise specifications of what constitutes evidence of students' language proficiency in assured assessment and how AI use is designed and declared in open assessment. This mirrors recent sector advice to balance assured and open assessments while preserving academic integrity safeguards (Liu & Bridgeman, 2023; Lodge et al., 2023; TEQSA, 2024).

GenAI can accelerate EAP content and assessment development by generating banks of reading and listening texts, writing task prompts, and speaking scenarios based on university-relevant themes. By specifying genre features and targeted language level in the prompt, teachers can tailor GenAI outputs to diverse curriculum needs. This streamlining revolutionises resource-heavy assessment development, supporting frequent task rotation and assessment security, and helps keep content current with disciplinary themes common in Australian universities. However, thorough human vetting is always required to ensure outputs are accurate, level-appropriate, and free of inadvertent plagiarism or copyright risk (Starford, 2024; Tran et al., 2024).

Another area of high impact is GenAI's enhancement of feedback processes. Teachers can use GenAI to draft formative comments that flag surface-level features and map them to rubric indicators. This automated generation of feedback frees teachers to focus on providing more in-depth feedback and feedforward. When students use GenAI independently to seek feedback, it can provide useful responses that are timely, easily accessible, and presented in a clear, digestible language that supports understanding (Henderson et al., 2025). GenAI can also help students identify areas for improvement in their work. Nevertheless, in skill-based domains such as writing, deeper learning and skill development can be undermined if students lack effective prompting skills, leading them to receive direct edits or suggested changes rather than formative feedback that prompts reflection on errors and scaffolds the reorganisation or rephrasing of their ideas (Luhach, 2024).

Interestingly, empirical research comparing students' perceptions of AI-generated and teacher feedback reveals that while students value the immediacy and availability of AI responses, they place greater trust in teacher feedback, describing it as more "relational, contextualised, relevant, and reliable" (Henderson et al., 2025, p. 12). This suggests a complementary nature between the two sources of feedback, in which AI handles first-pass feedback, while teachers provide more tailored feedback, calibration, and next-step guidance (Henderson et al., 2025).

This aligns with Australian feedback literature that emphasises learner uptake and interaction over mere information delivery (Jensen et al., 2023). When turnaround times are reduced or resources are limited, teachers can combine AI-drafted feedforward with self-assessment using rubrics, exemplars, and brief viva checks to preserve the social aspect of feedback (Boud & Molloy, 2013; Jensen et al., 2023).

Scalability gains are particularly notable in ELICOS centres with multiple intakes across 10- to 20-week programs. GenAI can assist teams in producing level-specific versions of reading-into-writing tasks, alternative prompts for discussion questions, or refreshed teaching materials that foreground current Australian debates (e.g., AI in research and academic integrity). Where direct entry comparability is required, productivity gains can be channelled into developing learning and practice materials (e.g., practice tasks or annotated exemplars) while secured, invigilated assessments continue to elicit unassisted language production for decision-making, consistent with TEQSA's aforementioned ELICOS Direct Entry expectations (TEQSA, 2023).

While GenAI can improve efficiency, it does not automatically produce classroom-ready materials or assessment tasks. The initial exploration by Chapelle et al. (2024) of the use of ChatGPT in generating reading texts shows that early versions of AI-generated texts were longer than required, included inaccurate information, and used vocabulary more advanced than specified; consequently, producing fit-for-purpose texts required multiple iterations, more detailed prompting, and significant post-editing. In assessment development, GenAI may generate workable multiple-choice stems and answer keys, as human assessment developers do; however, it often struggles to create plausible distractors (Chun & Barley, 2024). Uncritical use of GenAI outputs can thus yield teaching and assessment content that contains factual errors, perpetuates cultural biases, or is pitched at an inappropriate level and therefore unfair (Chapelle et al., 2024). Students may also find AI feedback repetitive or less trustworthy when it is not tailored to their work and to the program's materials, assessment tasks, and rubrics.

To mitigate these risks, EAP programs should implement sound assessment and feedback design principles, require thorough review and vetting processes, and build staff capability. Providers should raise teachers' and assessment developers' critical AI literacy (Chapelle, 2025) and strengthen their evaluative judgement capability (Bearman et al., 2024). One practical step is to require staff to critique AI outputs against robust criteria and annotated exemplars before adapting and

integrating these outputs into assessment materials. Established item-writing guidelines, such as those outlined by Haladyna (2004) for multiple-choice items, remain useful supports in this process.

IMPLICATIONS FOR ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND ASSESSMENT

Beyond improving efficiency, GenAI has broad implications for English language teaching and assessment due to its cognitive impact on users. Recent research on the thought processes of GenAI-assisted essay writing reports that GenAI support reduces engagement of the brain networks involved in internal idea generation and monitoring. It is also associated with weaker memory and a diminished sense of ownership (e.g., poorer ability to quote one's own text) compared with unaided ('brain-only') writing and search-engine-assisted writing (Kosmyna et al., 2025). The authors characterise this as 'cognitive debt': short-term fluency gained with GenAI at the expense of deeper learning, with carry-over effects when students later write without assistance (Kosmyna et al., 2025). These insights have implications for both language teaching and assessment. The authors recommend instruction that engages unaided and search-engine-assisted writing skills, as well as GenAI-supported writing, to develop a broad range of skill sets.

As EAP programs in Australia continue to operate in the age of GenAI, the question is how to integrate these tools in ways that preserve the existential function of developing learners' language proficiency and academic literacies for university studies while developing their AI literacies and ethics.

Curricula should specify where GenAI is permitted in language learning and assessment, as well as how it is restricted in assured assessment. The two-lane approach to assessment (Liu & Bridgeman, 2023), alongside more detailed frameworks such as Perkins et al.'s (2024) five-level AI Assessment scale and Steel's (2024) six-lane framework, offers a pragmatic path: a strategic combination of open, learning-oriented tasks in which students use GenAI transparently for brainstorming, sourcing, and drafting support under teacher mediation and secured, invigilated checkpoints that elicit unassisted performance for progression or university entry decisions.

Given the reported reduction in neural engagement with the use of GenAI in writing (Kosmyna et al., 2025), programs could consider withholding the introduction of GenAI tools in early stages. They could start with brain-only writing activities to develop students' ability to produce English independently,

before progressively incorporating search-engine- and GenAI-supported activities. Assured checkpoints should then collect a sample of unaided planning and information integration (e.g., reading-to-write responses), while open tasks make the use of GenAI visible and teachable.

Pedagogically, genre-based teaching may remain central, but it should be extended to include critical work on prompts, acknowledgement and citation of AI-mediated ideas, verification of claims, and comparison of human- and AI-produced exemplars. To counter ‘cognitive debt’ (Kosmyna et al., 2025), teachers can embed practices that activate thinking and planning in the writing process. Where AI assistance is used, they can design tasks that require students to explain their evaluative judgments and present their critical reflections. Pairing process evidence, such as planning notes, version histories, and records of incremental improvement based on feedback, with brief viva voce sessions should be normalised so that teachers can triangulate learning without defaulting to policing or surveillance.

Professional development for assessment developers and teachers must now include AI literacy alongside language assessment literacy. These staff require access to institutionally approved AI tools and opportunities to develop practical AI use capabilities, with an understanding of tool affordances and limitations, so they can generate outputs supported by reliable sources and calibrated to a specified level of linguistic sophistication. They also need to develop skills in auditing outputs for level, accuracy, and bias; designing AI-assisted feedback that students can utilise; and documenting AI use in a manner consistent with institutional policy and sector standards. Equally important are privacy and data security protocols for handling student work. Time saved by AI-enabled drafting and first-pass feedback should be deliberately reallocated to high-value activities, such as diagnostic assessment, oral language development, modelling of paraphrasing, summarising, citation, and GenAI use, and targeted language enhancement activities, rather than being absorbed by administrative tasks. Program leaders can support this shift by providing shared prompt libraries or rubric-aligned comment banks.

These changes reimagine the role of the EAP practitioner. Beyond serving as a materials writer and assessor, the practitioner becomes a curator, a coach, and a designer of evidence: curating task inputs to sustain local authenticity; coaching evaluative judgement so students can appraise AI outputs against criteria; and designing coherent, and, where feasible, programmatic assessment that combines

AI-supported learning with credible, comparable assessment decisions. The practitioner also acts as a policy translator between institutional governance and classroom practice, ensuring that AI use declarations, authorship checks, and assured assessment methods are proportionate and educative. When used deliberately, GenAI can augment teacher expertise in areas such as expanding variation and currency in tasks and accelerating feedback cycles while allowing EAP teachers to focus on the human work of making expert judgements and providing targeted guidance and support that enhances student learning.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CLASSROOM RESEARCH

The integration of GenAI into academic and professional domains has fundamentally altered how language is produced, refined, and evaluated by educators, students, and employers, prompting new standards for communication, critical thinking and authorship across diverse contexts. As such, it is reasonable for English language development to assume a degree of human-AI collaboration. The question remains, however, as to what level of human-AI collaboration is appropriate, for which tasks, and under what conditions in EAP programs that assess a student's English language proficiency. There is certainly an argument to be made that, as English language use evolves, so too must the ways of assessing EAL students' readiness for university study.

For EAP program providers, classroom-based validation and external benchmarking are necessary to establish evidence that new assessment regimes, which include AI-incorporated assessments, yield valid, fair, and comparable inferences about proficiency, comparable to those of international language proficiency tests. A related question is the continuing role of international proficiency tests in determining readiness, particularly where students' skilful and ethical use of GenAI may mediate their ultimate academic success. Research should therefore examine how unaided performance and AI-mediated performance jointly inform decisions on progression and entry.

Nonetheless, to critically engage with, refine, and ethically deploy AI-generated content within academic contexts, students must possess a strong level of language proficiency. It remains the task of EAP programs not only to develop core linguistic skills, but also to cultivate a broader set of academic and digital literacies. These include critical reading, information literacy, genre awareness, and socio-pragmatic competence alongside digital fluency and ethical reasoning. By fostering these skills, EAP programs empower students to collaborate effectively with

teachers, peers, and GenAI, navigate complex academic tasks, and contribute confidently to university-level discourse.

EAP educators are uniquely positioned to observe and evaluate how students interact with GenAI in academic tasks, providing valuable insights into the linguistic competencies required to use these tools effectively and informing the pedagogical shifts needed to support ethical and critical engagement. Several interesting research pieces provide direction for future research options in EAP, for example:

1. Hawkins, Taylor-Griffiths and Lodge (2025) explore how students use GenAI for feedback during essay writing, finding that feedback literacy and the ability to evaluate essay outputs are significant predictors of essay performance.
2. Haidar and Tassis (2025) investigate the perceptions and integration of GenAI among EAP instructors, finding that rather than seeing GenAI as transformative, instructors largely view it as a supplementary tool to enhance existing practices.
3. Roe, Perkins and Tregubova (2024) introduce the EAP AI Assessment scale to guide ethical and pedagogically sound integration of GenAI into EAP instruction. Their five-level scale has use cases at each level offering recommendations for implementations and future research in this field.

CONCLUSION

EAP programs in Australian higher education are undergoing significant transformation as they respond to the dual pressures of technological innovation and regulatory compliance. Through evolving curriculum design, assessment reform, and pedagogical adaptation, these programs aim to equip students with the academic literacies, intercultural awareness, and digital competencies necessary for success in university studies. The case studies of Macquarie University College and Monash College English Language Centre illustrate how institutional policy and classroom practice are beginning to engage with the possibilities and challenges introduced by emerging technologies such as GenAI. Ultimately, the capacity of EAP programs to strike a balance between 'innovation' and 'accountability' will determine their effectiveness in preparing students for the demands of contemporary higher education. In practice, this balance, as illustrated

in the two centres' examples, can entail pairing transparent, GenAI-supported learning tasks with secure, invigilated checkpoints that evidence unaided performance; documenting process evidence (e.g., drafts, prompts, vivas); and building staff capability in AI literacy and evaluative judgement. Ensuring responsible and effective integration will require a collaborative, interdisciplinary approach that brings together educators, technology specialists, applied linguists, and policymakers to co-design frameworks that uphold academic integrity while enabling innovation and supporting comparability with external admissions criteria.

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